

“Development of Nutritious Cookies Using Banana (*Musa paradisiacal* L.) Fruit Pulp”

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Abstract:

Cookies represent a major segment of bakery items consumed globally. Growing awareness of health and well-being has led consumers to shift toward healthier and more nutritious food choices. Poor dietary practices are associated with the development of various health disorders. In view of these concerns, the partial replacement of wheat flour with alternative ingredients is considered necessary to reduce gluten content and improve the physicochemical quality of cookies. This study aimed to develop and innovate cookies using banana fruit pulp as the main ingredient. This study evaluated the effects of banana fruit pulp on selected chemical properties of low gluten cookies. The present study concludes that partial substitution of wheat flour (variety-Lokwan) with banana fruit pulp positively influenced the nutritional and chemical quality of the cookies. The chemical analysis of the finally developed cookies indicated that the energy, protein, carbohydrate, fat, moisture, ash, and total sugar contents varied within the ranges of 333.7–468.6 kcal/100 g, 3.49–15.68%, 57.98–75.25%, 6.16–19.39%, 5.44–

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17.07%, 0.96–1.86%, and 18.86–34.23%, respectively. Furthermore, the mineral analysis revealed that the potassium, sodium, and calcium contents of the cookies ranged from 144–583 mg, 123–876 mg, and 231–424 mg, respectively. Based on their chemical characteristics, the cookie formulations C₀ (100:00), B₂ (80:20), and B₄ (60:40) were found to be more acceptable than the other formulations. Among the different formulations, the optimized blend showed desirable quality characteristics and acceptability, indicating its suitability for large-scale and commercial production. Hence, banana fruit pulp can be effectively utilized as a functional ingredient for the development of value-added, nutritious cookies. All cookies were prepared without the addition of any preservatives.

Keywords: Cookies, Gluten, Banana fruit pulp, Wheat flour, Chemical analysis.

Introduction:-

Cookies are considered as an important bakery product because of their extensive consumption around the world. Cookies are famous for affordability, convenience, and nutritional value (Johnson *et al.*, 2023). Generally, cookies are recognized as flat, hard, and crunchy foods and hence more favored.

Bananas (*Musa* spp.) are one of the world's most important fruits consumed worldwide. Banana name comes from Arabic word 'Banan' which means finger (Singh *et al.*, 2018). In 2021, India exported 341 thousand tons of bananas (FAO Stat, 2021). Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Gujarat, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh,

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Maharashtra, Odisha, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal are the largest states in India that produce the most bananas (Singh *et al.*, 2018).

Banana is rich source of potassium (K), which benefits muscles and keeps body fluids in balance. In certain areas, mashed banana is given to a new born infant as their first food. Banana is the ideal food for toddlers, persons with disabilities and those with HIV/AIDS (Aurore *et al.*, 2009). Coeliac disease is an autoimmune disorder caused by intolerance to gluten and affects both adults and children. Management of the condition requires strict avoidance of gluten-containing foods. As a result, individuals with coeliac disease cannot consume products made from wheat, barley, or rye.

The present study was undertaken to develop a high-quality and nourishing snack by incorporating banana fruit pulp with wheat flour (Lokwan variety). The objectives of the study were to formulate cookies using banana fruit pulp and wheat flour and to evaluate their chemical properties along with overall acceptability. The findings of the study indicate that banana-based cookies can serve as nutritious, cost-effective, and consumer-acceptable food products.

Raw Materials:

The raw materials used for the preparation of cookies included wheat flour, banana fruit pulp, baking powder, baking soda, brown sugar, ghee, salt, milk, and packaging materials. All ingredients were procured from the local market of Chalisgaon, District Jalgaon, Maharashtra, India.

Preparation of Cookies:

Composite flour prepared from wheat flour (Lokwan variety) and banana fruit pulp was used in accordance with the treatment plan. Brown sugar and ghee were creamed together until a light and fluffy consistency was obtained. banana fruit pulp was then incorporated into the mixture, followed by the addition of wheat flour (Lokwan variety), baking powder, baking soda, salt, and milk to form a uniform dough. The dough was shaped into desired forms and baked at 180 °C for 15 minutes. After baking, the cookies were allowed to cool and were subsequently packed in low-density polyethylene (LDPE) pouches. The packaged cookies were stored at ambient temperature (28–32 °C) for stability evaluation. The prepared cookies were further analyzed for their chemical properties at SHHLOK Food Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar.

Proportions for Cookie Formulations:

The cookie formulations were prepared using different proportions of wheat flour and banana fruit pulp. The control treatment (C₀) consisted of 100 per cent wheat flour without the addition of banana fruit pulp. Treatment B₁ contained 90 per cent wheat flour and 10 per cent banana fruit pulp, while B₂ comprised 80 per cent wheat flour and 20 per cent banana fruit pulp. Similarly, B₃, B₄, and B₅ were formulated with wheat flour and banana fruit pulp ratios of 70:30, 60:40, and 50:50, respectively.

Chemical Analysis of Cookies:

The chemical composition of the cookies was determined by analyzing their

energy value, protein content, carbohydrate content, fat content, moisture level, ash content, total sugar content and mineral composition, including potassium, sodium, and calcium. These parameters were assessed to evaluate the nutritional quality of cookies fortified with banana fruit pulp. All chemical analyses were carried out at a certified food testing laboratory. The testing of cookie samples were conducted at SHHLOK Food Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, India.

Observations:-

Analysis of Raw Materials:-

Table 1. Chemical Composition of Banana fruit pulp and Wheat Flour

(Variety: Lokwan)

The results of physio-chemical parameters of Banana fruit pulp and Wheat Flour (Variety: Lokwan) are presented in Table 1.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Banana fruit pulp	Wheat Flour (Variety:Lokwan)
1	Energy (kcal/100g)	87.5	390.6
2	Protein (g/100g)	1.35	12.8
3	Carbohydrates (g/100g)	19.44	80.68
4	Fat (g/100g)	0.4	1.98
5	Moisture (g/100g)	76.85	6.30

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6	Ash (g/100g)	1.82	0.30
7	Total Sugar(g/100g)	0.9	0.0
8	Potassium (mg/100g)	882	126
9	Sodium (mg/100g)	08	565
10	Calcium (mg/100g)	99	410

Chemical Composition of cookies:-

Table 2. Chemical Composition of cookies using Banana fruit pulp and Wheat Flour (Variety: Lokwan)

The results of physio-chemical parameters of final developed cookies are presented in Table 2.

Sr.No.	Parameters	C ₀ 100:00	B ₁ 90:10	B ₂ 80:20	B ₃ 70:30	B ₄ 60:40	B ₅ 50:50
1	Energy (kcal/100g)	468.6	423.5	441.4	333.7	376.8	383.6
2	Protein (g/100g)	15.68	4.45	4.82	4.76	4.85	3.49
3	Carbohydrates (g/100g)	57.98	75.25	74.25	65.81	66.62	68.57
4	Fat (g/100g)	19.39	11.65	13.91	6.16	10.13	10.59
5	Moisture (g/100g)	5.44	7.67	5.85	9.59	17.07	15.56
6	Ash (g/100g)	1.53	1.02	1.29	0.96	1.34	1.86
7	Total Sugar(g/100g)	34.23	20.03	19.83	19.54	20.04	18.86

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8	Potassium (mg/100g)	144	327	144	375	583	513
9	Sodium (mg/100g)	123	479	375	633	674	876
10	Calcium (mg/100g)	424	251	247	241	236	231

Values are mean of three replicates

Figure: Graphical representation of chemical parameters of final developed cookies.

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Result and Discussion:-

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The data collected on various parameters were systematically analyzed, and the results are presented both in tabular and graphical forms for better clarity and interpretation. The physico-chemical properties evaluated included energy (kcal/100 g), protein (g/100 g), carbohydrates (g/100 g), fat (g/100 g), moisture (g/100 g), ash (g/100 g), and total sugar (g/100 g). In addition, the mineral composition of the cookies—namely potassium (mg/100 g), sodium (mg/100 g), and calcium (mg/100 g)—was determined. These analyses were carried out for cookies prepared using banana fruit pulp incorporated with wheat flour (variety-Lokwan). The results of the present study are comparable with the findings reported by Sawant BB *et al.*, (2023), Pandey *et al.*, (2020) and Shelke S.A. *et al.*, (2024).

Conclusion:-

Based on their chemical characteristics, the cookie formulations C₀ (100:00), B₂ (80:20), and B₄ (60:40) were found to be more acceptable than the other formulations. All cookies were prepared without the addition of any preservatives. The chemical analysis of the final developed cookies indicated that the energy, protein, carbohydrate, fat, moisture, ash, and total sugar contents varied within the ranges of 333.7–468.6 kcal/100 g, 3.49–15.68%, 57.98–75.25%, 6.16–19.39%, 5.44–17.07%, 0.96–1.86%, and 18.86–34.23%, respectively. Furthermore, the mineral analysis revealed that the potassium, sodium, and calcium contents of the cookies ranged from 144–583 mg, 123–876 mg, and 231–424 mg, respectively.

The present study concludes that partial substitution of wheat flour (variety-Lokwan) with banana fruit pulp positively influenced the nutritional and chemical quality of the cookies. The incorporation of banana fruit pulp enhanced key parameters such as energy, macronutrients, and mineral content, thereby improving the overall nutritional profile of the product. Among the different formulations, the optimized blend showed desirable quality characteristics and acceptability, indicating its suitability for large-scale and commercial production. Hence, banana fruit pulp can be effectively utilized as a functional ingredient for the development of value-added, nutritious cookies.

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